

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF SURGE AVOIDANCE SYSTEM WITH ESD SYSTEM

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Abstract

In this paper, the integration of anti-surge control (ASC) and Emergency Shutdown (ESD) is examined as a means to enhance reliability by addressing faults within the system components. The paper discusses the surge phenomenon in compressors, identifies surge precursors, and outlines potential damages resulting from surges. It also delves into surge avoidance methods in modern compressors equipped with surge control systems, including their practical applications. Additionally, it elaborates on the sizing of system components and valves, emphasizing methodologies for accurately estimating suitable upstream pipe sizes. The paper evaluates existing surge protection techniques for compressors, discussing their respective advantages and disadvantages. Furthermore, it explores new approaches for detecting system changes and surges, offering insights into future perspectives.

Keywords: Centrifugal gas compressors, turbomachinery, control system, emergency shut down, surge avoidance system

1. Introduction

Compressors play a vital role in the oil and gas sector, facilitating the transportation of gas over long distances by elevating its pressure. The operational constraints of centrifugal gas compressors are pivotal, revolving around flow, speed, and head. At a desired speed, centrifugal compressors attain maximum head, accompanied by an equivalent flow termed as the limit of stability. Stability is maintained when head remains low, indicating minimal friction within the compressor, and flow surpasses the lower limit. Consequently, the system's stability remains unaffected even if reduced head leads to increased flow. Surge, a critical issue, occurs when a compressor operates at maximum load capacity, resulting in minimum flow. This surge is prevalent in low-frequency pulse systems due to the dynamic nature of compressors. Flow reversal transpires when the compressor fails to meet the required head under

discharge and suction conditions imposed by the compression system.

Surge, a phenomenon occurring in compressors, involves the reversal of flow and acceleration of compressor speed to the speed of sound. This cyclic occurrence inflicts substantial damage to the compressor and poses risks of human injury. Various operational scenarios can trigger surge, including uncertainties in volumetric flow, suction pressure variations, disparities between discharge and header pressure, compressor startups, emergency shutdowns, and other factors. The repercussions of surge extend beyond the compressor itself, potentially causing oscillations in the system and damaging nearby piping connected to critical systems, leading to hazardous situations and overall system efficiency reduction. The figure №1 below illustrates different surge maps [1].

Figure 1. Surge maps

When a compressor reaches its surge limit, components such as impellers and diffusers may approach stall conditions. Stall occurs when gas separates from the flow surface, often due to fluctuations in the aerodynamic components' incident angle. Similar to the airfoil concept, an increase in incident angle eventually leads to stall conditions. In turbomachines, stall is frequently observed as rotational instability, with confined

regions of separated flow moving alongside the diffuser at speeds lower than the impeller's rotational speed. Surge compromises the stability of the system.

Attempting to increase series resistance within the compressor to elevate compressor head to its maximum value can disrupt process stability. In such cases, the flow rate declines, causing a corresponding decrease in

compressor head capacity. This decline in head capacity further reduces the flow rate. When the compressor fails to attain the required external head, flow reversal occurs, leading to surge. Surge not only hampers process objectives but also induces radial and axial rotor movements that can inflict severe damage on the compressor.

To gain a comprehensive understanding of compressor surge control system working conditions, we outline typical applications that necessitate the utilization of surge control systems:

1. Surge control systems, particularly centrifugal compressor setups, are frequently employed in pipeline compression applications. Surge occurrences are inevitable due to flow variations managed by the pipeline, spanning the entire compressor's pressure ratio range.
2. Compressors play a crucial role in re-injection applications, where gas is injected back into potential producing fields. These applications require variable discharge pressures aligned with the fluctuating gas field pressure requirements.
3. Gas collection facilities gather production-type gas mixes for processing or transmission pipeline applications.

Installing a control valve as a bypass in the compressor system provides effective prevention against surge occurrences. Temperature and pressure transmitters are strategically positioned along the compressor discharge and suction lines, with a differential pressure transmitter utilized for flow measurement through the compressor. A control valve, dedicated to surge protection, along with a control system algorithm, completes the setup. An anti-surge system utilizes instrumentation data for flow, temperature, and pressure to define the compressor's operating point. This operating point is then compared to the compressor surge limit, and the control error is calculated as the variance between them. To mitigate such risks, a recycle valve is often installed in the compressor to operate during surge conditions, thus averting potential damage [2].

2. Phases of anti-surge control design

Figure 2. Typical anti-surge control system model

Gas composition variations during operation significantly impact compressor speed, as evidenced by changes in the machine's Mach number. The 'H' notation signifies the mathematical relationship between head and flow, providing a modeling basis for surge limits irrespective of gas property fluctuations. Surge limit model parameters can be determined by measuring the head across the flowmeter and the compressor.

Modern anti-surge control (ASC) design incorporates five essential elements:

- Accurate surge limit model: The surge limit model should accurately reflect the gas characteristics and operating conditions.
- Precise control algorithm: The control algorithm should adeptly prevent surge while accommodating process variations.
- Proper instrumentation: Instrumentation selection should prioritize accuracy, range, and speed.
- Suitably selected recycle valve for the compressor: Recycle valves must be compatible with the compressor, capable of swift and significant capacity adjustments.
- Properly selected recycle valve for system volumes: The recycle valve should prevent surge limit attainment during shutdowns, necessitating fast and substantial valve response.

In earlier iterations, surge controls operated pneumatically, utilizing differential pressure through flow measuring devices to control surge. With advancements in technology, particularly the advent of micro-processors, surge protection systems evolved to accommodate modern, high-stress-bearing compressors. These systems employ advanced mathematical modeling, such as polynomial-based surge limit models, and introduce balanced control systems. Contemporary surge control focuses on maximizing the compressor's operating zone [3].

2.1 Surge control system model

ASC systems are implemented to prevent surge events in compressors, requiring rapid response times with minimal impact on the process. Understanding the conditions conducive to surge is crucial for effective prevention, as accuracy in surge avoidance leads to an expanded operating zone for compressors. The parameters defining the compressor's operating zone include speed, head, and flow, with surge and the compressor's operating zone being mathematically related using these parameters. Figure №2 below illustrates a comprehensive layout of a compressor.

Calculation of the head across the compressor and the flowmeter yields parameters such as temperature, compressibility, and specific gravity, which can be eliminated from both equations to simplify the equation. The resulting equation represents reduced head versus reduced flow, as illustrated in Equation.

$$H_p = K \cdot \left(\frac{P_d}{P_s}\right)^\sigma - 1 / \sigma \cdot T \cdot SG \cdot Z$$

$$H_{Reduced} = \frac{\left(\frac{P_d}{P_s}\right)^\sigma - 1}{\sigma}$$

Various relationships are involved in defining the operational range of the compressor. One of these relationships concerns the ratio of pressures for the compressor, denoted as "Rc". This ratio is elaborated upon below.

$$R_c = \frac{P_d}{P_s}$$

$$\sigma = \log \left\{ \left(\frac{T_d}{T_s} - \frac{P_d}{P_s} \right) \right\}$$

$$qr^2 = \frac{\Delta P_{os}}{P_s}$$

Where P_d is the discharge pressure of the compressor; P_s is the suction pressure; σ is the polytropic head

exponent; T_d is the discharge temperature; T_s is the suction temperature, qr^2 is the reduced flow, and ΔP_{os} is the differential pressure across the flowmeter.

These sensor values P_d , P_s , T_d , T_s , and ΔP_{os} , are utilized in defining the algorithm to control the actuator. Control response is generated due to rapid changes in the system. Oscillations may occur in the system when gains are set very high.

As the surge avoidance system is often idle, waiting for surge to occur, it must take aggressive action without any deviation to protect the compressor. This may require very high gains within the stability zone. Gains are reduced to avoid instability outside of the system. Once surge is prevented by the anti-surge system, the control system should resume the process at an optimum rate to minimize the chances of upsets [4].

2.2 Anti-surge control system design

In the shown system Figure № 3, Active Surge Control (ASC) model is implemented, controlling surge using advanced torque control with variable frequency drives.

Figure 3. Conventional Surge Control System

In some references an effective surge control system simulated for emergency shutdown scenarios, testing two competing methods with simulation and validating results for hot and cold recycle valves. An anti-surge valve is controlled using a closed-loop response derived from the model and a safety margin, initiating the closed-loop response using the load variable from

the model. While producing correct results in the presence of nonlinearities, this controller's stability is not commented on [5].

In other references design a fuzzy logic control framework, effective for nonlinear systems and self-predictive, independent of compressor map information (Figure № 4). The derivative is feedback to tune membership functions, reducing error and making the system more robust [6].

Figure 4. Fuzzy Anti-Surge Control System

Overall, various conventional and advanced surge control techniques rely on parameters such as flow, speed, head, pressure, vibration, fuzzy residuals, or gas

leakage for surge detection and prevention. These parameters are crucial for surge control, as outlined in the table №1.

Table 1.

Simple and advanced methods of ASC.

Description	Parameters measured
Conventional Methods	Flow Speed Head Pressure
Advanced Methods	Flow-Speed Ratio PLC-based Control Vibration Temperature VFD Torque and Hot Recycle Valve Fuzzy Residuals Surge Protection Line Compressed Air Passing

2.3 Selecting the proper instrumentation

To achieve optimal results, the instrumentation should be selected with a resolution, accuracy, and speed that exceed the requirements of the system. For instance, if a compressor's first-time constant is approximately 1 second, instrumentation with a time constant of less than a hundred milliseconds should be utilized. Additionally, the accuracy level of the surge control system should ideally be within 0.1% of the process measuring instruments' range. Considering that changes around 1% in the input signal can be resolved by the recycle valves (final elements), the resolution of the process variables should ideally be 0.1% of the standard range of operation. It's worth noting that the resolution may be compromised by over-ranged transmitters. The flow measuring device is preferably installed on the compressor suction side [7].

2.4 Surge control valve

The response of the controller to sudden and gradual changes during surge conditions has been previously addressed. Similarly, the operation of the valve must align with these two scenarios. For gradual changes, the valve should provide subtle adjustments, akin to a small valve or with smooth action, ensuring steady and controlled operation [8].

The properties of valves can typically be categorized into three types (Figure № 5):

1. Quick action: The initial part of the valve's opening cycle achieves its maximum capacity.
2. Linear: The valve's opening corresponds directly to its capacity.
3. Equal Percentage: The maximum capacity is reached toward the end of the valve's travel.

Figure 5. Commonly observed inherent flow characteristic types

Installing a valve with equal percentage properties can prevent surge during shutdown scenarios by ensuring sufficient capacity. Furthermore, maintaining firmness is crucial for capacities below 50% to effectively control partial recycle action. When fitting the compressor, valves with equal percentage properties offer

greater resolution compared to those with linear properties.

When larger volumes are present on any side of the compressor, the approach typically involves the use of multiple valves. In the integrated method, valve capacity may be reduced.

Figure 6. Hot gas bypass valve parallel to main surge control valve

For quick action, the inner or hot valve operates in an on-off manner, while the outer or cold valve serves as the controlling type (Figure № 6). Each valve is sized individually. If the cooled valve is a solenoid-type

valve, the shutdown valve capacity matches that of the cooled valve.

Another scenario involves installing an additional valve in parallel to the existing one, as depicted in Figure № 7;

Figure 7. Paralel cool gas bypass valves

The size of the recycle valve for a compressor is determined by its operating conditions, which are input into a valve sizing program. This program considers various parameters such as compressor details, cooler specifications, relief valve settings, and pipe pressures. From this data, the program calculates the flow coefficient (C_v) or valve capacities.

Suppliers of surge control valves provide key parameters like C_v , X_t , and C_g values, which are crucial for valve selection. Surge control valves typically operate based on the equal percentage property. Once selected, these valves are designed to operate effectively under different conditions, with their travel reaching two-thirds level during surge.

Flow rate calculations follow the ISA standard method, where the flow rate (Q_{std}) is determined considering the geometry factor of the piping (F_p), often assumed as one unless otherwise specified. Constant pressure is assumed throughout the pipe volume, both downstream and upstream of the valve.

Typically, the capacity of the valve remains constant at the surge limit of a compressor.

$$\frac{dp_2}{dt} = \frac{k \cdot p_2}{V} [Q - Q_v]$$

$$Q_{std} = 1360 \cdot F_p \cdot c_v \cdot Y \cdot \left[\frac{p_2 - p_1}{p_2} \cdot \frac{1}{SG \cdot T_2 \cdot Z_2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$Q_v = Q_{std} \frac{\rho_{std}}{\rho(p_2, T_2, Z_2)}$$

This dependence isn't solely on the outgoing flow from the compressor. The pressure drop across a valve is largely influenced by the size of the pipes, meaning larger volume pipes experience fewer pressure drops. The operating point of the compressor plays a crucial role in calculating the discharge pressure.

$$\frac{p_2}{p_1} = \left[1 + \frac{k-1}{k} \cdot \frac{h(Q, N) \cdot SG}{287 \cdot Z T_1} \right]^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \frac{h}{N^2} = \alpha \left[\frac{Q}{N} \right]^2 + \beta \frac{Q}{N} + \gamma$$

Additionally, a flow and head relationship is derived using a lookup table. During Emergency Shutdown (ESD), the behavior of the compressor is directly influenced by these two properties. Among these properties, the turbine, coupling, and compressor inertia (J) play a significant role in ESD conditions. The other crucial parameter is torque, which directly interacts with

the fluid. These properties collectively determine the response of the compressor during an Emergency Shutdown scenario.

The torque is calculated as:

$$T = -2\pi \cdot J \cdot \frac{dN}{dt}$$

The gas power can be calculated by taking into account the torque, inertia, and changes in speed, as demonstrated below:

$$P = T \cdot N \cdot 2\pi = - (2\pi)^2 \cdot J \cdot N \cdot \frac{dN}{dt}$$

The proportionality factor (k) remains constant for both speed and power, regardless of whether a rundown event occurs at any operating point. Similarly, the deceleration rate during shutdown, which is determined by k and J , remains independent of the compressor's operating point. The flow coefficient (C_v) of the recycle valve is divided into two parts: one for steady-state flow during normal operation ($C_{v,ss}$), and the other for flow during surge conditions ($C_{v,avail}$). Given the values of $C_{v,ss}$ and C_v , the available portion of the flow coefficient, which can be utilized to reduce backpressure, can be calculated as follows:

$$C_{v,avail} = C_v - C_{v,ss}$$

The compressor typically operates at a fixed temperature, and most compressors are equipped with coolers to regulate the system temperature. These coolers have a thermal capacity much larger than that of the gas, leading to negligible temperature variations within 1 second [9].

The equation for flow calculation deducts the discharge-occupied gas, resulting in changes in piping volume and pressure. This interpretation identifies the maximum available actual volume of the piping under given constraints, ensuring complete avoidance of surge during Emergency Shutdown (ESD).

3. Integration of anti-surge control with Emergency Shutdown System

In this paper, we examine the dynamic characteristics of a compressor station during emergency shutdowns, emphasizing the significance of surge preven-

tion for safety and operational reliability. Our investigation aims to assess the suitability of valve dimensions, speed of opening, and the configuration of single or multiple valves. The integration of hardware redundancy with analytical redundancy enhances system reliability but incurs higher costs. Therefore, a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis is required before implementing the unified Emergency Shutdown System (ESD) system [10].

4. Conclusion

This paper provides a comprehensive review of Anti-Surge Control (ASC) systems for centrifugal compressors. It examines various techniques for measuring parameters such as speed, flow, head, temperature, surge lines, and flow speed ratio to detect and prevent surges.

Furthermore, the paper reviews the importance of considering sensor and actuator failures alongside system design, algorithms, and control parameters. The objective is to minimize damage during surge events, enhance compressor efficiency in fault conditions, and reviewing plant response in surge events.

Throughout the discussion, the paper highlights the significance of integrating ESD into ASC systems and introduces a novel idea for its implementation. The proposed approach aims to improve the overall reliability and performance of ASC systems.

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